

DESTIGMATIZING THE STIGMA: A DISCUSSION ON MENTAL HEALTH
AMONG FIRST-GENERATION STUDENTS OF COLOR

by

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Abstract

As we evolve and progress throughout the decades, more and more research is conducted within more specified fields of study. Whether these studies reveal vital contributions or rather minimal discoveries; the ability to simply expand one's knowledge on a topic to its fullest intent is phenomenal in of itself. In this paper, the extents of mental health within communities of first-generation students (of color) will be observed and discussed via ethnographical methods, conclusive statistical data, and a detailed literature review. Although studies on mental health are extensive; see (Bracke, 2019; Kalkbrenner ,2021; Lipson, 2018) the subject matter itself is relatively new. There is substantial research surrounding the topic, but not much of it is specific to BISOC (Black, Indigenous and students of color) first-generation students, or, at the very least, not many of these studies address the experience of first-generation BISOC at universities like CSUF (Pedrelli 2015; Jenkins 2011). This research seeks to inform readers about the variety and discrepancy of mental health and how the role of a community, family, and even peers can factor into one's own mental health. This study primarily focuses on the mental health of first-generation students of color to represent their experiences; and contribute to other studies regarding mental health and its relation to first-generation students of color (Lipson 2018). The findings of this study are meant to reveal possible patterns, recognize factors that affect mental health, and determine possible solutions to the mental health concerns of first-generation students of color. It is in hopes that addressing such a specific topic will shed light onto the issue, further propelling more decisive research on the matter so that if a trend on mental health is observed, the shaping of a path towards help begins to develop more concretely to ensure the next generation of students have even more access to help.

INTRODUCTION

The intention of this paper is to recognize, facilitate, and continue the discussion surrounding mental health, specifically how cultural stigmas can be prevalent in the worsening of mental health among first-generation students of color and how said stigmas persist, continuing a generational cycle that continuously harms its community. This paper responds to a lack of discussion within this marginalized community and thus will provide insight on an issue not frequently addressed. Before diving into the study, the paper will discuss and explain the independent variables that tie the project together. Concepts such as mental health, first-generation, students of colors, and cultural stigmas will be defined so that the reader may develop a better comprehension of the subject matter and apply their own perceptions to the best of their knowledge. Once a familiarity of each term is developed, a shift into corresponding literature will be reviewed and discussed so that a sense of understanding can be established when piecing together the topics interrelatedness.

Most importantly, after reviewing the literature and relevance of research pertained to the topic, the paper will shift into a more qualitative examination and insight revolving around the prospects of mental health and its corresponding framework. I use a first-person, auto-ethnographic evaluation explaining the decisions behind the development of this work. Furthermore, the paper will also explore three other participants who all meet the scopes of the study's focus. These participants were recruited from a survey that focused on a more quantitative approach to mental health, although the survey would not serve academically significant to the findings of this paper. The three participants were informed that their identities would remain anonymous and that the informal interviews conducted would include notetaking. After receiving consent from all three participants, analyzing the notes taken, a qualitative

assessment of the informal interviews would be evaluated, reported, and discussed. The discussion portion of the paper would provide context and understanding behind the participants' experiences and behaviors regarding the scope of the subject matter and would explain the correlation between the autoethnographic portion and the case studies. It is in the hopes that through the discussion portion of this paper, a clearer image of the cultural stigmas placed upon mental health will be considered and discussed more thoroughly and extensively. In no way is this project intended to shift cultural traditions, or spark means of agitation or turmoil, it is simply intended to illuminate respondents' experiences of outdated cultural stigmas.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Bhugra's et al., (2013) definition of mental health is perceived in three ways, one that correlates mentality to an absence of a mental disease, another that recognizes mental health as an organism fulfilling its functions, and, lastly, the recognition of a balance within oneself and their physical well being and socio- environment (Bhugra et al. 2013). In the original survey provided to the three participants who discussed their own experiences within the frameworks of the study, a set definition for the term "mental health" was provided. This definition was that directly cited from the Oxford Online Dictionary and defined mental health as "a person's condition with regard to their psychological and emotional well-being" (Oxford Online Dictionary, 2021). The respondents were given the choice to either provide their own definition to the concept of mental health or confirm that the definition provided was one they felt was accurate. All three respondents accepted the Oxford definition as the most accurate. Within both examples defining mental health, one specified, the other simplified, the sense of a mental/psychological well being comes into play. That, of course, would correlate to the term "mental health" itself, recognizing that the statement identifies the well-being of one's mental

environment. Regardless of the definition, the result is the same, being that mental health and its studies align with understanding how one's own psychological well-being plays into their daily life; whether their well being can lead to mental disorders, stressors, or concerns and how said components are handled completed the "health" aspect of the term. Mental health, then, becomes a definition of which can be interpreted more personally by those who experience symptoms of worsening mental health. This is further solidified when analyzing Shavitt's et al., questionnaire on perceived mental health where the questions regarding an individual's personal perception on their mental health were only scaled by measuring symptoms of depression (Shavitt, et al., 2016). For the sake of this project, mental health is measured by each participants willingness to express whatever they felt most attributed to their mental health, whether experiencing symptoms of depression, anxiety, stress, etc., each participant could convey their own experiences that validated the worsening symptoms they observed in their own mental health.

Corresponding to the topic of mental health, the stigmas persistent to mental health and its resources remain prevalent among first-generation communities of color (Lindsey et al., 2010). In this piece, Lindsey stresses the significance of communal and familial intervention when addressing critical symptoms of mental health, specifically, an observed trend within African American boys to pursue means of support in fear of negative familial reactions. These preestablished stigmas serve as gates to preventing association with any means of mental health disparities. Even more troubling, Yamaguchi et al., discusses an observed trend of college students ranging from ages 18 to around 24 revealing that they are actively aware that they experience symptoms of worsening mental health, but do not act upon receiving resources or help in fear of stigmas from within their own community (Yamaguchi et al., 2013). Recognizing the reality of stigmas and how they persist among various communities maintaining a chokehold

on individuals from seeking means of aid or assistance is one of the primary reasons for this projects' fruition. Stigmatized ignorance or attributions to cultural barriers are far too harmful to not only previous, but also current, and future generations within the specified framework; these marginalized communities already suffer enough from external pressures, internal pressures, and preconceived perceptions, our own culture and practices should not be another factor on the list.

Stigmas, although already a leading focus in this study, operate differently in different cultural contexts. However, the specificity of this study is one that targets aspects that meet the criteria of dealing with mental health, studying in a college environment, having to deal with preconceived stigmas, and, of course, being a first-generation student. Being a first-generation student can attribute to various meanings, whether simply being born first-generation outside of a different country or recognizing oneself as a beginning to a new family genealogy, the recognized similarities fall within the scope of new and upcoming life within an unfamiliar context. The definition observed within the specs of this study refers to what is universally recognized as "first-generation" (Pease, 2013). Within agreement to Pease's definition of first-generation, typically this study aims towards the age group that falls within 18-22 and whose parents never attended any means of higher education post-high school. Pease, however, also discusses a newly recognized definition of being first-generation, one more particularly angled to parents of first-generation students not having completed an undergraduate degree but maintaining minimal time in college. In this study, the former more accurately represents the target study group as all three participants fell within Pease's initial definition. Recognizing the preceding factors that contribute to being first-generation, however, was not the only means of identifying with the first-generation experience. Stebleton et al., (2014) discusses this much more thoroughly in his piece regarding mental counseling among first-generation college students.

Stebbleton emphasizes disadvantages and barriers placed among first-generation students, some of which cannot be observed in their non-first-generation counterparts. These disadvantages include age, disabilities, lack of citizenship, financial independence and struggle, familial turmoil, and even broken English (Stebbleton et al., 2014). Although not explicitly having to meet any of these additional requirements to meet the identification of a first-generation student, the three participants of this study would all meet multiple disadvantages and detail the way their identity as first-generation students shaped both their educational career and their mental health.

The final component behind the framework that shapes this project is identifying as a student of color. The professional inclusion of this phrase would represent those students who fall within the umbrella term Black, Indigenous Students of Color (BISOC). To identify the students of color that centralized the premise of this study more accurately, Sutter and Perrin had their own students answer a subscale identifying racial and ethnic discrimination and then had their students answer their experiences of racism from a scale of 0 (never having experienced racism) to 5 (experiencing racism more often than once a week) (Sutter and Perrin, 2016). This model reflects an individual's own receptions to racism around them and, although not a method that considers all factors contributing to racism, it would provide the study an observation of how racism is dealt and managed when considering only self reported experiences. Although nowhere near as scrutinous, the participants of this study all identified with their ethnic and racial minority upbringings and recognized themselves to fall within the term of BIPOC. Observing Lipson's et al., study on mental health disparities among college students of color, a more straightforward approach was taken. Each student would be able to opt-in their own means of self identity, including racially identifying as white, in which Lipson would then measure the results of the students of color and compare them to their white counterparts. This method would

prove effective at distinctively identifying not only whether a student identified as being of color, but also accurately represent that student's ethnicity and nationality, permitting Lipson to pinpoint a range of mental health issues and the ethnic groups most and least affected more accurately by worsening symptoms (Lipson et al., 2018). Recognizing the extents of which this study focuses on, in the context of racial identity, proves critical into understanding the differences and disadvantages students of color, whether in an education or social environment, face daily. This study will amplify the experiences of several first-generation students of color. Barr and Neville, in their piece regarding racial socialization, discovered that, specifically among Black college students, those who grew up with no perception upon racial socialization or color-blind racial ideology displayed trends towards more negative mental health outcomes. That is, if parents have actively forewarned their children on issues regarding their ethnic/racial identity, perceptions of racism and sense of belonging and its effects on their mental health can differ vastly in comparison to those who were never socialized (Barr and Neville, 2014). In no way is the reference behind this specific study intended to attack the parents, family, or community of children who were mentally affected by an unawareness of racism; however, the study proves relevant when considering different perceptions of discrimination and racial prejudice within the participants of this study.

METHODOLOGY

This research-based project followed a standard review of literature, examining preestablished findings correlating to the main arguments and deciphering concepts of mental health, stigmas, first-generation, college students of color, and culture. Via the comprehensive examination of previous research, the project then shifted into a more interpersonal examination of the subject via a hybrid ethnographical dissertation and multiple case studies of personal

experience of the subject. Through the autoethnography, the study will permit the reader to pursue a deeper understanding of the writers' personal ties to the topic and how the project developed from there. Conversely, the study also pursues a higher understanding of the respondent's experiences, which, within the context of this study, refers to the in-depth ethnographic discussion of others, within the specifications of this research, who were willing to divulge their experiences and realizations dealing with mental health stigmas and perceptions and how their stories amplified a greater understanding of the issue at hand. This means of ethnographic research that deterred from a standard, structured interview pertains to H. Russell Bernard's own practices of informal interviewing. Bernard discusses the importance of informal interviewing within ethnographic fieldwork, specifically, when stepping outside the formal, and diving within the crude reality, a sense of realism is required, one that does not pertain to protocols or regulations (Bernard, 2006). Within our experiences and mental insecurities, there is no set of restrictions or methods of properly dealing with mental health issues, they simply exist, allowing these participants to simply discuss what they experience without requiring them to follow a structured guideline provides this study a sensation of crudeness and authenticity.

The aim for this comprehensive study was to also include a greater sample size of direct reaction and responses to concepts of mental health and their interrelatedness to the greater population of first-generation students of color at CSUF, however, the survey had a low response rate. Instead, using the few students that did complete the survey, three students, who showed interest in discussing their experiences in detail, were reached out to, and from there the project was able to maintain meaningful case studies that directly related to the topic at hand. Despite not applying the contents of the survey to this study, all three students who have shared their stories regarding their experiences with stigmas, mental health, and identity have contributed

meaningful data to the further development of mental health studies, specifically mental health within marginalized communities.

Beginning the initial process of pursuing the development of this study, there was a rather clear idea of how the framework of the project to intended be shaped and how, subsequently, the research would present. However, considering the project heavily revolved around the scope of mental health and its severity, multiple self sabotaging obstacles would present themselves that would place time constraints and shift the frameworks of the project to the ones present now. Despite these initial setbacks, the project remained centralized on the qualitative value of the human mind and ultimately, conveyed equal amounts of relevant data that maintained the original scope of the study.

This project is one of personal value that allows a deeper dive into one's mind to open and break down persistent yet ignored aspects of mental health that gnaw at multiple people who reflect similar identities. Being a first-generation student of color, it became ever more important to highlight and discuss aspects of mental health that are not addressed publicly or as frequently as they should be. Thus, allowing for this research project to consist of not only ethnographical research of other student's experiences, but also maintain the value of auto ethnographic contributions became rather clearly early on. Stepping into oneself mind and then publicly revealing the issues dealt with is a difficult yet vital decision to make. The project would then provoke the question "If not me, then who?" and would further propel the desire to share the experience of dealing with pressure, stigmas, and identity and how it could serve a higher purpose by contributing to further developing arguments against harmful cultural persistence and paving the way for others to be willing to share the interpersonal relatedness of the topic at hand.

Finally, as mentioned earlier, the final component of this short-term ethnographic researched based project is one that examines the value and vulnerabilities behind the stories of the respondents. Originally, the plan was to formulate interviews reflective of the survey research data with relevant questioning and a meaningful sense of direction. However, once more, the framework would shift to a cruder, yet pure and informal interview/discussion where the student, who would remain anonymous, could wholeheartedly reveal the pressures, mental instabilities, and obstacles they were dealing with and be able to direct the discussion in whichever direction they deemed fit. There were instances in which intervening with generalized questions relating to the topic was needed; however, most of the discussion was unscripted and raw and pertained to the students' own experiences and values regarding the topic. As the discussion initiated, each student was ensured and asked for consent regarding notetaking where they were once more informed that the findings of the discussions would remain anonymous in both the final dissertation and the official presentation of the study in which all three students provided their consent. Through the notes, analysis of each student's experiences in relation to the comparative value of both the autoethnographic aspect of the project and the relevant data would be compared and discussed. In this comparison, aspects of similarities and differences will be highlighted, noted, and discussed so that meaningful components of data are revealed and placed into the spotlight of dissection. The comparative analysis will then provide insight on possible patterns, stigmas, or values that retain to the significance of the project and how these components of analysis can be deciphered or understood by the public.

DIVE INTO ONESELF

The premise of this project revolves around the importance of mental health and how we can address both aspects of culture and stigmas specifically targeting these first-generation

students of color. However, the project did not necessarily come to light with this specified intention in mind. Instead, the project originally developed through various phases varying from cultural analyses to mental health and its underlying effects on social science majors. As I began to envision what this project would look like, I realized that it was not necessarily meeting the criteria I wanted it to meet. Around this time, I had been experiencing waves of tiredness, exhaustion, and initial symptoms of failed motivation. I thought nothing much at the time since I had to worry about classes, work, and familial life. At one point, in developing the senior honors project, I began having doubts and uncertainties about whether I really wanted to incorporate geography into my project. I had already developed concepts for specific types of maps, quantitative data, and spatial data analysis that could contribute to various sorts of geographical research but pursuing any of these concepts to their full extent felt draining and uninteresting. This was also around the time that I began doubting my desire to pursue higher education, specifically, I felt I was wasting time on studying something I did not truly care for. I pondered why I had even wanted to pursue higher education in the first place since I would vividly recall struggling mentally to please both my family and me academically throughout high school. This was a beginning shifting point that would begin to reshape what would become my project.

After reevaluating why I had pursued higher education after having felt so mentally drained from high school not even 5 months prior, I realized rapidly that the entirety of my life, I have never considered the alternative to not pursuing higher education: disappointment. Since I could feasibly understand prospects and desires, the integration of education and its values have been embedded into my mind. There was never really an “option” for me as a person as to whether I would pursue higher education or not, it was always going to happen because it was expected and demanded. Not only did I serve as the leading role model for my brother and

cousins, but I also served as a talking piece; a means to boast for my family; a means of “breaking the chain,” and my purpose was to fulfill the dream that I never had. Upon reflection, it may be possible that even if I was never pressured or led down this path, I would pursue high education regardless. Removing the opportunity for an immigrant child to decide what they will accomplish within the frame of their own life already deems that child incapable of dreaming, as they can only dream what their family dreams for them. This would mark the second shift that would deter and alter the framework of the project.

The guilt, resentment, and distaste for both myself and the pursuit of higher education would linger as I continued my studies. It would now be time to concretely decide what the study of my project would be, and I would have pondered countless different possible topics, but only one would stick. Discussing mental health and how important it comes at the cost of informing others that the reason mental health is so important is that it resonates to you. Mentors, professors, and peers alike all enjoyed the idea of shifting my topic to that of mental health; it was academically based, and it would require ample amounts of research. In the end, however, the project would only be conceived because I, myself, was feeling the piling pressures and tolls that coincide with worsening mental health. Self-doubt, sabotage, and resentment were now frequent emotions, and I could not understand why.

I would piece together components of my identity and would talk to various peers, friends, and familiars alike, and slowly, I would begin to realize why I wanted to pursue a project so focused on mental health. Absorbing reactions, thoughts, and statements alike, I noticed how minimal conversations of mental health can be simmered down to. That is, whether one would respond to a question regarding their health positively or negatively, the result would be similar. Another component to the ever-growing framework of the newly shaped project would now

centralize in pursuing discussion upon mental health to be more than small conversation pieces, and instead outlets of interpersonal values and meaning, with both parties consenting to this.

Personal identity would be another premise of which I would have difficulties both addressing and identifying. I then recognized that it would serve rather well as another framework behind the specs of the project. I am an immigrant child from a destabilized country who had to acclimate to the environment around me while also upholding values that were not my own; I am a first-generation student of color who persists in education because that is what I have been raised to do. Despite not knowing whether this path was the one I wanted to pursue, it is the one I have been placed within and because of that opportunity, I want to ensure that I can provide a space for those willing to discuss the contents of this study.

Recognizing my place in this world, not just as a first-generation student of color, but instead as my own person, I realized that I was placed in a generational cycle of stigmas, taboos, and cultural barriers that I no longer wanted to uphold. Dealing with both aspects of mental health and tackling the extremities of life, I noticed how belittled perceptions on mental health were within my community. Whether it be around my own family, or friends, preconceptions on dealing with mental health are played off or blatantly disregarded and I realized that this would finalize the specificity I wanted to convey in my project. The generalized framework of the project that had originally been vastly different had now been finalized and it would soon be time to solidify my findings, sources, and research question. I felt that this project was now much more than a means of graduation, it was a sense of identity and a reflection of my character.

As time hurried on, my mental health would continue to deteriorate at a rapid pace and once more symptoms of self-doubt and self-sabotage would plague my mind. Various times throughout the project's development, I would ponder simply quitting on the project and simply

going on with my educational career with no regard to the aspect of the project that was the most important: discussing mental health. Throughout those episodes of doubts, I truly believed that discussing my issues with my mental health with others would work at propelling me to continue. For the most part, these discussions would help momentarily and give me a small nudge towards completing the said project. At one point, once more, I felt that I was at an all time low. I was attempting to follow deadlines, class projects, and course seminars, but I never once felt that I was authentically developing the project the way it deserved to be. One of the lowest points in my pursuit of the project was when I had given my word to mentor, peers, and professors alike that I would finalize the writing process throughout the summer. During those three months, I had absolutely no motivation to pursue the writing process, or any process for that matter and I would inevitably let down the people around me and the people who supported me.

Realizing that, regardless of whether I could keep true to my word, those around me would still push me forwards and encourage the completion of this project, I dug myself out the sinkhole I had dug myself in. Mentor, peers, and directors alike, once more, would place their faith in me and would, conversely, provide avenues of support and kindness. These avenues, although familiar to me via educational means, had felt out of reach during this entire process. I finally decided to step out of my own head and reach out to means of mental support that would identify and recognize possible issues pertaining to what I had been dealing with. A direct recommendation to the Counseling and Psychological Services (CAPS) at California State University, Fullerton would initiate my journey of mental healing and cultural resistance that I, myself, had felt was out of my reach.

My journey began as typical as most others, simply conversational diagnoses with a consultation. The consultation process would last over three sessions and would explore components of my life I felt attributed to my symptoms of mental health decay. Discussions regarding my childhood, educational career, personal life, family life, and work life would all be addressed and evaluated. There were times where I felt that too much of my life was being entrusted to a stranger, yet, at the same time, I felt as if there was never enough time to cover all the hardened surfaces that could possibly explain aspects of my mental health in ways that were more specified. Hearing a licensed professional place terms and diagnosing the symptoms I have been experiencing was a rather frightening moment in my life. For so long, I have been avoiding the reality of the issue, the possible problems with my mental health, yet there I was officially being diagnosed. I could no longer hide behind the façade of not knowing because it was crudely revealed. The consultant of my journey would work alongside me with exercises intending to destress and evaluate the lengths I had ventured and to recognize where I was now. It was then recommended to me that I pursue longer means of therapeutic services in which I could express the pains and troubles I had endured and recognize that none of what I experienced should be diminished or pushed aside.

I recognize this part as the predominant factor that would push me to complete such a heavy topic. It was no longer about just me or my inefficiency, or my self-doubt, or whatever other walls I would place. This project was so much more now, it was about breaking a generational cycle, one that would persist if we failed to recognize the reality of the matter. I would comply and continue with weekly therapy sessions in which I would be able to discuss the effects my family life had on my development or discuss the astounding pressures that I felt being the first of my family to pursue higher education while maintaining an image of success.

However, despite now having my own means of support, I was still too afraid to let my family or even those closest to me know that I was actively seeking assistance. I decided then that it would be crucial for me to seek out means of discussion through alternative methods such as the qualitative case studies of other first-generation students of color willingly able to have a conversation on the topic.

All three participants were able and willing to convey what they felt mattered to the development of this project. They were able to detail and discuss their own inner doubts and mental issues recognizing that it would be a discussion that would propel further initiation to understanding other ethnic minority groups and their attitudes towards harmful cultural stigmas. I credit these individuals who stepped up also knowing that this project was much more than our hesitations and self doubts. I can confidently state that without their assistance, cooperation, and stories, I, myself, would have been incapable of also stepping outside of my boundaries and discussing the inner turmoil that has been plaguing me for this period. Recognizing that there is so much more to offer from our narratives and from the recognition of the harms our own cultures may have, I would then proceed to convey and express the very own stories of the three individuals who each contributed to igniting the spark.

A DIVE INTO THE CASE STUDIES

{TRIGGER WARNING: SENSITIVE MATERIAL}

Discussing personal experiences with mental health demands an ethical approach, trust, and confidence, not because it is an insight into ones own personal experiences, but because it is through the contents of the material that a better understanding of what mental health and the crude reality of it is. To some, mental health and its corresponding symptoms and adverse effects

are minimal, temporary, or overlooked, to others, mental health and its effects can be suffocating, prolonging, and even harmful. No two people experience the same extents and symptoms of mental health, as no two people approach dealing with mental health similarly either. Through the stories conveyed in this study, an attempt to not only justify but also validate the various expression of mental health issues is pursued so that anyone reading this paper can come to terms with any inner issues they had been pushing aside. The participants in this study all were willing to share portions of their lives in which they have felt the most vulnerable, the most damaged, and the most in pain. For the sake of not only their person but also those around them, the participants in this study are to be coded and remain anonymous. Participant number one will be referred to as M1, participant two as L2, and participant number three as S3. Each individual participant is more than just a participant, they each convey narratives, experiences, emotions, and a sense of humanity. Through their consent, detailed notes regarding each participant's behaviors, key points, and direct statements have all been jotted down and shall be presented when relevant. Furthermore, each participant was willing to share dark moments of their life characterized by emotional abuse, trauma, suicidal ideation, and other sensitive issues, thus, a warning on upcoming sensitive material has been issued.

M1: WITHIN THE SENSE OF ALIENATION

“Growing up having to prove ourselves to not only our people, but those who don't even look like us, imagine how exhausting that can be” (M1, 2021). Placed into an environment in which they felt eyes were constantly drawn towards them, how can a place that advocates diversity feels so alienating. M1 grew up within the confines of their community, a place of low income, but high social and ethnic relation. They have felt comfortable, for lack of better words, navigating through elementary and high school in that they always had peers and friends who

could share similar stories about their upbringings. This sense of placement, belonging, it would vastly deter once they reached the realm of higher education. California State University, Fullerton, a campus deemed for all, what other environment could be as accessible and as diverse as the campuses they have already endured. Yet, when they first set foot on campus, all was but familiar. In an environment they once imagined familiar and close to home, the eyes of outsiders and strangers were now locked on to them. An immediate sense of alienation and panic, for the campus they were excited to explore no longer displayed the values they once saw. O'Neal et al., understand this sense of social alienation all too well. Within the frames of institutional barriers, whether citizens or noncitizens, Latino college students perceived a sense of social isolation and exclusion; an environment that was not catered to people who resembled them, or even people who maintained the same values (O'Neal et al., 2016). M1 was experiencing these symptoms no differently than any other ethnic minority student, the sense of dread, of not meeting expectations, of not being “worthy” enough to be here, M1 had never felt any more alone.

Despite recognizing this sense of isolation when placed in an institution not catered to people like them, M1's issues with mental health were also byproduct of familial and religious interference. Having almost no motivation to do well in their courses or even to work, M1 would be subject to constant belittlement by their own family. Lazy, ungrateful, and undisciplined were only but a few of the names they endured while dealing with their symptoms of anxiety, depression, and imposter syndrome. No one around them could understand the severity of their issues, the reality that school was not as easy as many take it to be, that they were already facing the pressures and obligations they never asked for. When approaching family to explain their mental battles, an ignorant yet frequent response would be thrown at them. “Simply believe more in our God,” as if religion was a staple method of dealing with mental health. M1 understood that

the generation before theirs grew up differently, that they were unfamiliar with issues outside the physical, but M1 also understood that there was no excuse to simply dismiss their own problems as if they were something they could just get over. Religion is not a viable outlet for mental counseling, whether it is talking to a priest, or attending weekly mass, the underlying issue isn't religious or spiritual, it is psychological. Aligning with Saechao et al., discoveries on stressors and barriers to outlets of mental health services, Saechao emphasizes the integral contribution both discrimination and parenting have on accessible outlets to mental health services (Saechao et al., 2011). Much like M1 discovered, parental involvement and a sense of isolation engulf their ability to pursue means of counseling and help. Whereas, in one corner, they feel that they must prove that they belong in a higher educational institution, in the other corner, they abide by their parent's lack of consideration regarding their mental health and navigate their career alone. M1's journey would not stop there, although not currently being able to tackle their own issues, they will be actively working on ensuring no more marginalized students feel the sense of inferiority they currently feel, they want to ensure that this generational ignorance regarding mental health is cleansed, or, at the very least, discussed.

L2: WITHIN THE SENSE OF FAMILY OBLIGATIONS

“While I am busy managing the hundreds of things in my life, at the very least, I have no time to think about my own problems” (L2, 2021). They remember vividly expressing shock when presented with the scouting survey, thinking to themselves that it was a miracle a topic like this could be brought to light. L2 grew up, and continues to grow, in an unfortunate and dysfunctional family. A family that, despite the constant changes in the household, upheld conservative and traditional values of which represented their family. No moving to America was going to diminish or alter L2's family traditions and ways of thinking. Immediately having

to make a living in this new home, L2's family had no time to pursue higher education, instead, it was off to work either in the navy or as a nurse. As L2's family would develop, it would be their task to raise their sibling while their family tackled the toils of labor. L2 would grow close to their siblings but would simultaneously have to mature earlier so that their sibling could be properly cared for and managed. In an environment where much was out of their control, L2 would sacrifice their childhood so that their siblings be cared for. L2 cared deeply for their younger brother, being that they were practically his guardian, but L2 would discover rather early on that their brother was not well psychologically. L2's brother would constantly act out, be hyper aggressive, and unstable, L2 realized that it must come to the attention of their parents. After medical evaluations and a prompted diagnosis, L2's brothers revealed signs of a mental disorder, a newly placed wedge in the life of L2. Bracke's et al., assessment of stigmatized beliefs on mental health services identified that people from countries that negatively associate aspects of mental health are much less likely to utilize available mental health services particularly due to their deeply rooted stigmatized beliefs (Bracke et al., 2019). In the case of L2's brother, it was no different. It seemed no one in L2's family had concerns with reaching out to counseling or special services that could help mitigate L2's brothers' mental disorder. In the mind of L2's family, this disorder was something that must be prayed away or ignored until fixed. L2 understood the severity and would retain much of their focus on helping their brother, but once again, this would come at the expense of L2's own mental health.

Dealing with their family's stigmas was not the only dominating issue at hand. L2 had a life of their own they had to endure, one where they never felt comfortable reaching out to anyone about. L2 would frequently emphasize that this generation gap between themselves and their family was far too wide for their family to ever truly understand L2's perspective. L2

adhered to the Christian values embedded into them, they even sought out to volunteer and serve the church they attended, but they also understood many of the values the church withheld were not shared entirely. One of these values would be a discussion piece for Bissonette and Szymanski on their piece regarding the correlation between depression and LGBQ college students. Both aspects of heteronormativity and religious indictment attribute to increases in stress and symptoms of depression among college LGBQ youth, in this sense, L2 was no different (Bissonette and Szymanski, 2019). This sense of separation from those you hold dear takes its toll; having to also refrain from speaking out about one's true self, was the situation L2 found themselves in. L2 would have to tackle their questioning identity while also maintaining their extensively busy schedule and their care for their siblings.

Days would merge, and deadlines would feel endless, yet L2 would have to maintain themselves for they were what withheld their family together. "We are not robots; we are not perfect people!" (L2). Every person has their limits, no matter how hard they attempt to push said limits. Balancing education, caregiving, work, volunteering, leadership roles, mentoring, and even teaching, at one point, one can only hope for an end. "Racial minority stivers, ... those who have been heavily college and career-inclined since childhood ... experience a phenomenon ... wherein they overburden themselves" (Kundu, 2019). L2's sense of being, or their purpose, has always been to do the most they can, yet most were never enough for them. Balancing their own life was difficult enough, yet there were also intended to balance the life of those they cared for. With no one to be there for them, L2 had to ensure they could be there for everybody else. To this day, L2 struggles profoundly with their symptoms of depression, with mood swings, anxiety, and with suicidal ideation. They discuss the pressures and baggage placed upon them as a byproduct of their own cultural stigmas and familial operations. They must seek approval from

those who are never willing to give it. Yet, they persist, despite the countless thoughts plaguing their mind, the countless days where they feel like they can go on no longer, they persist. L2 recognized that they cannot give up on themselves because that would be giving up on the future generation.

S3: WITHIN THE SENSE OF REALIZATION

“Studying the topic, you learn to recognize and categorize the symptoms, yet I can’t act upon mine” (S3, 2021). The final participant of this study was already all too familiar with the subject matter. S3 was pursuing a career in psychology, specifying that it was the current interest they had and the major they had selected. S3 mentioned that simply in the principles and beginning to psychology courses, mental health and its disorders are touched upon frequently. S3 would be able to recognize signs of mental distress and understand the vitality of reaching outwards for help. Yet, as observed within the trend of all others, S3 could not act upon mental health when it came to their own best interests. A strong advocate for the recognition of mental health, a component recognized thoroughly by Kalkbrenner’s et al., study on mental health literacy, S3 would constantly encourage peers, friends, and family alike to seek out mental health assistance, reflecting Kalkbrenner’s utility of peer-to-peer referrals (Kalkbrenner et al., 2021). S3 must rely on their own mental fortitude so that they can persist in an environment they deem harmful to them. This persistence, denial of help, S3 discusses how it roots from their own family at home. Within their household, issues of mental health or obstacles to work are only viable when physiology is in play. Family members only see the external wounds S3 deals with but dismiss any internal wounds S3 may disclose to them. They aim to be a psychiatrist, not because it was what they intended to be, but because they recognize it will make their family proud. The thing is, there is a great irony behind a decision to pursue a medical field centralized

upon mental health, yet not having one's own family recognize the severity of mental health. S3 recognizes their family's own traumas and mental blockages, but stigmas and taboos on mental health are not the only means of harming one's mental health. S3's family migrated to the United States hoping for a better future. Within this decision to build a new life, S3's family decided that pertaining to their old ways would only hinder S3's opportunities. S3 would grow up only speaking English, their nonnative tongue, but would still experience the world as a first-generation student of color. Within S3's own community, they felt persecuted and unbelonging, as if they were not "ethnic" enough to be recognized as part of said community. In that sense, S3 would characterize feelings of discrimination and prejudice when around their own extended family, a sense of nonbelonging that could be observed in published studies on discrimination within Hispanic institutions.

Serpas discusses daily discrimination and mental health within Hispanic serving institutions and how within these institutions, inflated rates of discrimination among non-Hispanic students of color were observed (Serpas, 2021). S3 corresponded with Serpas' discoveries, they experienced feelings of discrimination due to their inability to speak their native tongue. In an environment where S3 felt neither side of their ethnic makeup accepted them for who they were, one can only imagine the mental tolls the sense of isolation can have. Yet, once more, S3 would persist in studying and working and doing the most they could possibly accomplish. They, as the others did, recognized that without initiating a change, without studying the subject matter, and without educating the future generations, the generation cycle would continue; so, S3 withholds even now. "Although I can recognize the problems within me, I can pretend everything is okay, and by pretending, things eventually become okay" (S3, 2021). S3, like many others in the world, is willing to sacrifice an aspect of their life, an aspect that is

looked down upon, ignored, and disvalued, for the sake of the upcoming generation. They wish to serve as a steppingstone forward for those who feel that no one is there to represent them, so that more and more individuals can be aware that there is a persistence and a fight to break down harmful stigmas on mental health.

DISCUSSION

Evaluating and comparing patterns observed from both the autoethnographic portion and the case studies, trends related to the subject matter can be widely observed. Firstly, after discussing the interpersonal connection that ties my own personal experiences (?) to the topic of this paper, while also considering the implications provided through the multiple defined terms, the correlation between mental health, cultural stigmas, and the first-generation student of color identity seems rather apparent. Personal identity is a major influence in the dissertation of various studies, thus, the personal connection between the autoethnography to the study conveys the question: are these stigmas present? If they are, what can be done to deter said stigmas. Simply reading upon works from Bracke (2019), Jenkins (2013), Lindsey (2010), Lipson (2018), and others, a generalized understanding of both mental health stigmas and first-generation ethnic students should be clear. Furthermore, considering the versatility of the case studies revolving around the participants who all shared their narratives and experiences, a more established sense of pattern can be observed. Comparing the autoethnography to the case of M1, in which the recognition of white institutions and symptoms of inferiority and unrequited expectations interrelate both narratives convey that mental health, despite its differences, can carry vast similarities. L2 and S3 both acknowledge that they may not be able to help themselves, but instead pave the way for their upcoming generations so that this cultural barrier can be dismantled and taken out of the loop. In a similar manner, the auto ethnography depicts the sense

of sacrificing ones own troubled experience so that others can recognize and relate to their own mental health issues and reach out for help.

These findings, then, become important to more than just the participants, the findings become vital paths for other underrepresented groups who feel the need to reach out and ignite their own spark on issues they connect with. This initial discussion can make it easier for others who feel completely isolated or lost, or even hopeless. It serves as a talking piece that propels one's own drive to do more for the people around them. Finally, these findings shed light on the marginalized communities that do not receive equal amounts of dissertations or studies compared to their counterparts. It then becomes known to the public that mental health disparities and differences are valid no matter how minimal or extensive they may be. There is no need to be an expert in the field to discuss issues affecting thousands of people, there is only a need for drive and intention to serve as an amplification for the voices that go unheard.

Although attempts were made to cover most dominating contributors to mental health stigmas and the effects it has on first-generation students of color; time barriers and limited findings prevented a more in-depth analysis of more possible venues. However, another component that contributes to mental health and means of coping when having minimal access to mental health services is substance abuse. Characterized in more detail, Blume et al., discusses ethnic minority alcohol usage within white institutions and how symptoms of anxiety, depression, and stress push students to rely on alcohol as means of coping (Blume et al., 2012). Highlighting the importance of recognizing possible consequences and harmful alternatives to mental health counseling provides incentives for readers to recognize the severity of the issue at hand. Not having healthy ways of treating mental health leads to far worse methods of treatment, some of which can prove to be fatal. Keeping that in mind, this study did not dive into

the research behind substance abuse and mental health turmoil, it is important to be aware of other contributing factors to mental health struggles. Another component of which was underdeveloped in the process of writing this paper was reactions and possible mental health disparities observed among previous generations. There is recognition to first-generation students of color and the obstacle to mental health services; however, there is no equivalent research done upon the generation before these students and the reason behind maintaining the cultural stigmas present on mental health and its services.

Overall, recognizing patterns, understanding generational cycles, and chipping away at cultural stigmas are only the initial intentions of this study. A push towards dissecting and discussing stigmas and taboos, whether relating to mental health or not, should be made in the future where more and more students feel comfortable addressing possibly controversial topics. Even so, the focus of this study is still yet underdeveloped, and, thus, refining and researching the studies of this paper should be constant and frequent. Although there is no intention to diminish generation cycles, traumas, or traditions, this paper encourages further discussion from not only within the community but also from those around it.

CONCLUSION

Stigmas placed upon mental health persist now and will persist for years to come. However, recognition of these stigmas and moving forward with dismantling them will begin the step forward to greater change within the field of mental health. The reality of it all is, unfortunately, first-generation students of color are more prone to dealing with symptoms of mental health deterioration by themselves. Avenues of resources and guidance are plentiful, but, until the stigmas revolving around mental health are dismantled, trends like the ones observed in this study will be frequent. Current students already place much of their own mental stability at

risk to please those around them; this costly sacrifice will evidently take its toll, yet many understand that sacrifices such as this are necessary to ensure a future where everyone can account for their mental health.

Throughout this study, observations upon the prevailing stigmas, their connectedness to mental health, and even the correlation between being first-generation and students of color have been made. Whether recognizing the importance of self-reflection to create a greater cause than oneself or braving forwards and expressing one's story so that others may absorb and relate to this push towards change. Evidently, the hope of this paper is to propel forward students who have felt lost, underrepresented, and misguided, so that they understand that family is not the only means of support out there.

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